

THE IMPORTANCE OF PREVENTIVE MEASURES IN PREVENTING OFFENSES AMONG YOUTH

Arslonbek Kalandarovich Khudayberganov

**Deputy dean for youth affairs at the faculty of Dentistry,
Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy**

Abstract. This article analyzes the importance and effectiveness of preventive measures implemented to prevent offenses among youth. It describes effective experiences in crime prevention through methods such as conversations, awareness campaigns, psychological assistance, and public oversight carried out by the Deputy Dean.

Keywords: offense, prevention, youth, deputy dean, educational institution, spirituality

Main part. Preventive work is a systematic activity aimed at preventing the commission of crimes. Deputy Deans regularly conduct legal awareness events, psychological conversations, and roundtable discussions among students. Additionally, individual monitoring of students with social problems is established.

Practice shows that the following methods are effective in preventing offenses:

- Classes aimed at increasing legal literacy;
- Permanent monitoring groups at the faculty level;
- Monitoring conducted in cooperation with the socio-psychological service;
- Regular communication and consultations with parents;
- Ensuring student engagement (clubs, community work). The preventive activities of the deputy dean awaken a sense of social responsibility in the student's personality, encourage them to choose the right path in life, and strengthen moral immunity.

Conclusion

Preventive work plays a crucial role in preventing delinquency among young people. When the activities of the deputy dean in this direction are effectively organized, it serves not only to prevent crimes but also to shape the student as a conscious, socially active individual. Therefore, this work should be carried out continuously in every higher educational institution.

References

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